

ВПЛИВ СТРАТЕГІЧНОГО ПЛАНУВАННЯ НА РІВЕНЬ КОНКУРЕНТОСПРОМОЖНОСТІ РЕГІОНУ

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IMPACT OF STRATEGIC PLANNING ON THE LEVEL OF COMPETITIVENESS OF THE REGION

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Анотація

В статті розглянути питання визначення стратегії, стратегічного планування, обґрунтовано поняття конкурентоспроможності, визначено особливості конкурентоспроможності регіону та вплив стратегічного планування на рівень конкурентоспроможності регіону.

Abstract

The article examines the issue of defining strategy, strategic planning, substantiates the concept of competitiveness, features of regional competitiveness, and the influence of strategic planning on the level of regional competitiveness.

Ключові слова: регіон, конкурентоспроможність, стратегія, стратегічне планування, методика.

Keywords: region, competitiveness, strategy, strategic planning, methodology.

Strategic planning as a factor of regional competitiveness can be effective if several fundamental prerequisites are met:

1. A dualistic approach to the process of strategic management, the core of which is the planning function. The dualism is that, on the one hand, there should be an active strategic activity of the central government, aimed at spatial development and its harmonization with sectoral development while actively supporting depressed and problem areas. On the other hand, the development of democratic forms of regional management provides an opportunity for regions to implement their own socio-economic policy of regional development. The success of strategic planning can be achieved by finding a consensus in the strategic management of regions by the state and the main strategic levers of regional power. At the same time, the consensus must have a holistic and comprehensive nature, exclude opportunism in approaches, politicization and take into account the interests and positions of all agents of strategic interaction, from an individual and a subject of entrepreneurial activity to a subject of centralized state administration. The consensus should take into account the multivariate positions of the participants in the regional development process, and the strategic vision of development goals should be shared not only by the elite of the country and region, but also by a wide range of subjects of regional socio-economic activity.

2. Giving the region the opportunity to function as a self-organized system. The region acts as a megasystem, an element of which is the subsystem of regional competitiveness. When developing a strategic plan, it is advisable to take into account the factors that form the sphere of attraction or set of points, and all the decisions

of the regional system should ultimately be focused on this set. [5,9,14].

The strategic plan of regional development should be supported by mechanisms and tools for its implementation. Thus, an important component of the strategic plan should be the regional scheme of spatial socio-economic development of the region, which will allow to determine the types of territories of the region with the aim of determining economic, social, environmental, industrial and other types of regional policy in relation to them; to provide a description of the functional structure of these territories; analyze demographic trends and identify migration trends; to ensure the synchronization of the infrastructural strategy of the regional leadership, among which the most important are logistics and information. Ensuring the strategic development and increasing the competitiveness of the region is served by such a tool in the innovation management system as the regional innovation system, which is a set of subjects and institutions whose activities are aimed at implementing and supporting innovative activities in the region [11,13,15,18].

The economic development of most regions from the point of view of economic development and growth of labor productivity as an indicator of the process and result of development is connected with the expansion of the sphere of the post-industrial economy, which in turn determines the transformation of all social institutions [18].

In the process of strategic planning, the question of the horizon of strategic planning becomes especially relevant, which is caused by the limitation of the period of authority of regional leaders of the highest level and the limitation of the life cycle of enterprises, except for nationwide energy and logistics projects. Determining

the time horizon of strategic planning can be effective when using in an adapted form the model of organizational development of Ayzedis [10], which distinguishes separate stages of development and decline of the socio-economic system, or Greiner's model, which describes development through a sequence of certain crisis points [12].

The most widespread can be called the model of Ayzedis, who distinguishes the following stages: birth, childhood, maturity, flowering, stability, aristocracy, early bureaucracy, bureaucracy and death. The positive aspect of this theory is that a typology of possible problems and mistakes of managers has been developed depending on the stage of development [6, p. 135].

Greiner's model is described in detail in the monograph of Prof. V. Miklovda and others and adapted to the development of the region in this way. The first stage is based on creativity and takes place on the basis of the use of creative potential, and the main attention at this stage is given to issues of developing the region as a product and marketing aspects of its promotion to the state or international market of investments, labor resources, etc. This stage ends with a crisis of leadership, which actually means that the period of creativity in the process of strategic management of the region ends and conditions are created for the transition to the stage based on the leadership of the region. This stage involves organizational restructuring, implementation of organizational innovations. The danger at this stage is the bureaucratization of the middle-level management of the region, which causes a crisis of autonomy. The third stage of development, as characterized by the authors led by Prof. V. Miklovdo, based on the delegation of powers. This stage arises as a result of overcoming the previous crisis and includes restructuring of the organizational structure of the region's management, decentralization of functions and democratization of management. The democratization of management is based on public creativity and responsibility, but over time it leads to a crisis of control by the top management of the region. The next stage is based on the coordination of the development of the region's territories, the strengthening of the division of labor in the region, the allocation of strategic development zones. Territories or groups of enterprises that determine the economic development of the region can be included in such zones. It has been proven in scientific works that when this stage is passed, peculiar boundaries between the center and functional subdivisions arise, which has received the name of the boundary crisis. The last authors of the monograph highlighted the stage of development of the socio-economic system, which is based on cooperation. The development of the regional organization at this stage becomes possible under the condition of the formation of common values shared by the subjects of regional development. The importance of the formal structure is decreasing, the role of having a single management team, a single community in the region is increasing. This stage can end with a crisis of psychological fatigue, or a crisis of trust, when team members get tired of interaction and cooperation [7, p. 135 - 136]. Thus, the horizon of strategic planning is determined by the terms of the region's leadership, the

processes of organizational changes at the region's large enterprises, and directly by the processes taking place within the region's management system.

The object of strategic management is the dynamics of development, which combines the dynamics of economic development, the dynamics of technological development, the dynamics of demographic development, the dynamics of innovative development, the dynamics of social development, etc.

The horizon and objects of strategic planning are definitely related to the fluctuations of the dynamic series, which makes it necessary to predict the type of crisis, time, duration, depth, and causes of its occurrence. And in the development scenario, it allows laying anti-crisis preventive measures and methods of managing existing crisis situations. Such measures act as competitive advantages that contribute to obtaining bonuses even in crisis situations. During strategic planning, it is recommended to take into account crises that may arise at strategic enterprises of the region, which act as a business guarantor of the region's development. There is a point of view according to which a change in the environment is the cause of changes in the socio-economic system, but crisis situations are the impetus for change:

- those that may arise in the field of financial management as a result of inadequate management decisions regarding cash flows - liquidity crisis;

- which, due to the occurrence of unplanned deviations from the planned course of development, non-fulfillment of planned or normative indicators, received the name crisis of success;

- which, as a result of mistakes in managing potential and making strategic management decisions, which lead to a decrease in potential opportunities and the ability to be competitive, this situation takes the form of a strategy crisis [8, p. 135].

The methodological component includes a wide range of approaches to the development of a strategic plan. The most common is the program-target method, which ensures agreement between the goals and the costs of achieving these goals; a balance sheet method that allows you to draw up balances of resources and results of economic activity of the business sector of the regional socio-economic system, an indicative planning method that determines standards for the public sector and benchmarks for the business sector of the region.

Regional management of Ukraine mainly uses programmatic planning. There is a point of view that programmatic planning consists in the selection of the main goals of social, economic and scientific and technical development, the development of interrelated measures to achieve them within the specified time frame with a balanced supply of resources taking into account their effective use, i.e. built according to such a logical scheme: goal – ways – methods – means. In this case, the definition of the problem is not taken into account as the main orientation of goal setting.

The use of the program-target method of planning involves:

- definition of the problem, formulation of regional development goals;

- development and implementation of a program aimed at achieving goals;
- monitoring of the implementation of the program in accordance with the set goals.

The goals to which the target complex program should be directed are determined by the strategy of the social-economic-environmental policy of the state or its individual territory. The strategic goal of the development of the region and the decomposition of goals depends on the depth of the problem and the resource base for its solution.

In the general management theory, the problem is a gap between the desired state (first of all, the goal) of one or another system and its actual state. That is, solving the problem is a way to overcome this gap, a choice of alternative actions that will make it possible to move from the existing state to the desired one. Achieving the strategic goal of the region's development is based on solving a group of problems related to both the functional development of the region and the territories included in the region. When implementing program-target planning in the conditions of the complication of market relations, the definition of the system of goals is based on the study of the problem, first of all, in the functional section. In order to achieve the strategic goal of the development of the region, it is possible to highlight financial, economic, ecological, cultural or other problems.

The presence of the problem and its content determines the current goals of the system, the content of the set of actions, resources and deadlines. To develop a comprehensive target program, it is necessary to investigate the problem in the following directions: importance, time aspect of solving the problem, preliminary assessment of the effectiveness of solving the problem, decision-making conditions, the nature of decision-making, the nature of the model of the problem situation, the level of formalization of the decision-making process, the frequency of decision-making, types of solutions [3].

When applying the scenario method of planning and developing a competitive scenario, as the research showed, it is necessary to take into account the styles of organizational behavior of the top management of the region. I. Ansoff speaks about the styles of organizational behavior, which the specified researcher singled out two: incremental and entrepreneurial [1]. Incremental style is aimed at the implementation of traditional behavior with the minimization of deviations both inside the organization and outside it. Entrepreneurial style implies a desire for constant changes and improvement of the achieved state.

The two styles mentioned require different sets of levers in the mechanism of strategic management of the region.

The conducted research made it possible to identify the positions that differ in the specific content of managerial activity with each of the styles of organizational behavior:

1. The main factor of development.
2. Approach to management decision-making.
3. Criterion of development.
4. Model of development of the region of activity.
5. Type of response to environmental changes.
6. Priority type of management.

Regarding development factors, the entrepreneurial style of organizational behavior uses knowledge and information as the main factor that ensures the competitiveness of the region. The incremental style of organizational behavior is based on the use of traditional factors.

Organizational style of behavior affects the choice of approach to management decision-making. The incremental style mainly uses technical methods of decision justification, the entrepreneurial style uses creativity as the main method of determining ways to solve a business problem and, accordingly, making a decision.

The styles proposed by Ansoff consider different criteria regarding the development of the region. With the incremental style, the assessment of development is carried out on the basis of determining the growth indicators of the gross regional product, performance indicators, and with the entrepreneurial style, the main indicator of development is the growth of the share of the region in the market of technological products, especially due to innovative types of products or services, the growth of the quality of life in the region.

Accordingly, regional development models, which are applied to each of the considered styles of organizational behavior, have different contents. The incremental style applies the traditional model, while the entrepreneurial style calls for the application of the innovative model. Accordingly, the incremental style is characteristic of the inertial development model, and the entrepreneurial style is mainly characteristic of the competitive model.

Ansoff's methodological position regarding the styles of organizational behavior explains the type of response of the organization to changes in the external environment. In the case of the first style, the reactive type is carried out, in the case of the entrepreneurial one, the proactive type, which in a certain way shapes the external environment of the business.

And, finally, the incremental style of organizational behavior determines the use of operational and ongoing management in regional management, and strategic management in entrepreneurial management.

Thus, the strategic management of the region, which lays the foundation for strategic planning, is determined by a specific style of organizational behavior, uses knowledge and information as the main factor in the development of the organization, applies a creative approach to making management decisions, forms an innovative model of regional development [2].

Strategic planning should be carried out not only in terms of existing legislation, but also foresee trends in law-making activity, which confirms the thesis about the professionalism and competence of regional strategists.

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